

JCMST

NOVI SAD

2023

Supported by the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Science, Technological
development and Innovation of the republic of Serbia

ABSTRACT BOOK

11 – 13 October 2023

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad

Novi Sad, Serbia

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

61(048.3)

THE PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology (2 ; 2023 ; Novi Sad)

Abstract book [Elektronski izvor] / The 2nd PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology 2023, 11-13 October 2023, Novi Sad, Serbia ; [editor-in-chief Rajko Jović]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Medicine, 2023. - 1 USB fleš memorija

Tiraž 150.

ISBN 978-86-7197-742-5

а) Медицинске науке -- Нове технологије -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 126492937

Joint Conference on
Medical Science and
Technology
NOVI SAD
2023

Advisory Committee

Dejan Madić, Full Prof., Rector of the University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Asst. Prof. Dr. Niwat Keawpradub, President, Prince of Songkla University, Thailand

Snežana Brkić, Full Prof., Dean of the Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, Serbia

Assoc. Prof. Roengsak Leetanaporn, MD Dean of the Faculty of Medicine, PSU,

Thailand

Zoran Gojković, Assoc. Prof., Provincial Secretary for Healthcare

Zoran Milošević, Full Prof., Provincial Secretary for Higher Education and Scientific Research

Scientific Committee

President Duško Kozić, Prof. Dr., Vice Dean for Research, MFNS, Serbia

Co-President Assoc. Prof. Teerha Piratvisuth, MD Vice Dean for International Affairs

Scientific Committee Members

Snežana Brkić, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Branislav Bajkin, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Zoran Komazec, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Biljana Srdić-Galić, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Biljana Vučković, Assoc. Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Dragan Kravarušić, Full Prof., University of Tel Aviv "Sackler" Faculty of Medicine, Israel

Ludovico Abenavoli, Full Prof., University Magna Graecia of Catanzaro, Italy

Prof. Tippawan Liabsuetrakul, M.D., Ph.D. / Vice Dean for Research, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Joint Conference on
Medical Science and
Technology
NOVI SAD
2023

Prof. Surasak Sangkhathat, M.D., Ph.D. / Assistant Dean for Research, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Pasuree Sangsupawanich, M.D., Ph.D. / Assistant Dean for Hospital Affairs, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Prof. Boonsin Tangtrakulwanich, M.D. / Head of the Department of Orthopedics, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Srisurang Suttapreyasri / Associate Dean for Research and Graduate Studies, Faculty of Dentistry, PSU

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Karnsunaphat Balthip / Associate Dean for Research, Social Alliance, and International Affairs, Faculty of Nursing, PSU

Local Organizational Committee

Goran Stojiljković, Full Prof.

Mirela Erić, Full Prof.

Otto Barak, Full Prof.

Milica Jeremić-Knežević, Assoc. Prof.

Jasmina Boban, Assist. Prof.

Vedrana Karan Rakić, Assist. Prof.

Dubravka Klajić

Position 39

UNAUTHORIZED STIMULANTS IN FOOD SUPPLEMENTS – RASFF NOTIFICATIONS

Maja Amidžić¹, Jelena Banović Fuentes¹, Ljilja Torović^{1,2}

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia

988d15@mf.uns.ac.rs; 990d15@mf.uns.ac.rs

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Center for Medical and Pharmaceutical Investigations and Quality Control, Novi Sad, Serbia

Introduction: Following expansion of market availability of food supplements in the last decade and their widespread use, serious safety issues have been raised. In order to meet the expectation of the consumers, some producers have turned to the illicit and dangerous practice of product adulteration with unauthorized natural and synthetic adulterants. A crucial element of a food safety system is efficient data exchange, in Europe operating through Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF).

Materials and methods: The aim of this paper was to perceive the extent of food supplements adulteration with stimulants. For that purpose, the RASFF database was searched using the following criteria: food category "dietetic food, food supplements and fortified food", hazard category "composition" (2011-2022). Automatically extracted records were manually refined in order to select those related to stimulants in food supplements, which were individually verified and counted.

Results: Following aforementioned criteria, over a hundred notifications were extracted, revealing 181 occurrences of prohibited stimulants, including natural phenethylamines such as synephrine with 51 records, ephedra alkaloids (5), octopamine (4), aegeline (4), and synthetic stimulants: 1,3-dimethylamine (DMAA) with 96 records, oxilofrine (8), β -methylphenylethylamine (BMPEA) (6), 2-amino-6-methylheptane (DMHA) (6), isopropyloctopamine (3), and amphetamine (1). The number of recorded occurrences surpassed the total number of notifications, due to simultaneous presence of two or more illegal stimulants in one food supplement.

Conclusions: Adulterated food supplements has led and will most likely lead to serious consequences for consumers, especially in case of supplements adulterated with combination of stimulants exerting synergistic effect, where a number of cases of serious adverse events and even deaths were recorded. A multidisciplinary approach that includes scientists in food technology, nutrition and public health is essential to our ability to respond to the global problem of the illegal practice of using unauthorized substances in food supplements.

Keywords: food supplement, adulteration, stimulant, safety